

Critical Making Responsibility Framework. Extending an Academic Proposal to Support Reflexivity in Maker Communities

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Abstract

Bottom-up initiatives from maker networks across the globe, such as the first aid response during the outbreak of the Coronavirus, are currently showing how responsible innovation is happening outside the constraints of profit-driven large industries. We are witnessing the development of alternatives to DIY and making as a hobby. In this process, critical, socially responsible making and a professionalization of the maker-driven open hardware movement resembles how open source software became a widespread alternative to proprietary software. However, the positive societal, economic, and environmental impacts of the maker movement are still researched. The Critical Making project aims to gain scientific insights into the potentials of the maker movement for critical, socially responsible making in a participatory way. With both an academic and a practice-oriented audience in mind the project develops the Critical Making Responsibility Framework and a corresponding practical toolset to help reflect on core principles of critical making, such as social responsibility, sustainability, openness, inclusiveness. In this paper we present the emergence of the Critical Making Responsibility Framework and its current state. Also, we reflect on the experiences of makers having contributed to the development of the reflective toolset and discuss some of the challenges encountered along the way.

Keywords

Critical making, responsibility, reflexivity, criticality, grassroots innovation, social innovation

1 Introduction

Over the last decades a large and continuously growing ecosystem of DIY, makers, hackers, and innovators has emerged that produce innovations across all fields of applications. This development has shaken up the research and innovation system in many ways, from its culture of openness and collaboration to the democratization of production and personalized manufacturing. The maker community has become important for industry, who seek collaboration, but also for academic research, as a way to encourage

students to become more interested in science, technology, and engineering. Since making and makerspaces represent a distinct approach from conventional ways of innovation, academic interest in the practice has been on the rise.

Alongside the positive examples however, academia has been debating whether the promises of positive societal, economic, and environmental impacts of the maker movement are truly delivered. The Critical Making project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research Funding Programme, aims to explore this question, and has been engaging in participatory action research for the past year and a half, aligned with an integrated interdisciplinary approach to explore responsibility in making.

In this contribution, we present the current version of the Critical Making Responsibility Framework, embedded in a wider analysis of the current state-of-the-art on critical, responsible making and innovation practices. The Critical Making consortium has made use of the framework to create awareness about criticality and responsibility in maker settings and the framework has contributed to shaping the co-design of interventions. First experiences in co-developing specific toolsets, including concrete guiding questions, for researchers who engage makers in participatory action and for grassroots innovators in the field, e.g. makers, have gained positive feedback. In this paper we dive deeper into the applicability and usefulness of a self-reflection tool that allows the reflection process to be gamified, with reflexive questions as prompts. We hope that through this iterative process, the framework can become more practical, and useful for any grassroots community and project at different creative stages.

2 Current Approaches Towards Critical Making

There has been growing academic interest in the maker movement as researchers started to explore its innovation potential. The literature base on making is growing. Research interests span from educational opportunities (e.g. Halverson & Sheridan 2014, Vuorikari et al. 2019, Stilz 2021) to economic aspects (e.g. Anderson 2012, Fasoli 2017 & Tassinari 2017, Langley et al. 2017) and societal implications of maker communities (e.g. Millard et al. 2018, Menichinelli & Smith 2019, Kieslinger et al. 2021). In the following we concentrate our state-of-the-art analysis on the democratization potential, and potentials for social and responsible innovation.

2.1 Open, social and responsible innovation practice in making

Openness seems to be an inherent characteristic of maker practice. It appears as one of the central values of the global movement (e.g. Dreessen, Sheepers & Leen 2016). Many makerspaces explicitly state openness and sharing as one of their core values, and it is outlined in the Fab Charter that every branded FabLab commits to (Johns & Hall 2020). Open-source software and hardware are central to the practical everyday lives of makerspaces (e.g. Haldrup, Hoby & Padfield 2018; Tanenbaum et al. 2013). Sharing designs openly online is also a major factor behind the global expansion of the movement. The effect that the expiration of closed licenses of 3D printers had on the global maker scene showcases this. As the designs of previously only commercially available 3D printing technology became available, makers around the world embraced the new possibilities and open-source 3D printers were immediately developed, with some becoming closed-sourced again (Benchoff 2016).

However, there is a need to critically reflect the contested understandings of openness as it may also lead to tension within the maker movement (Saari et al. 2021) Openness is a multifaceted concept and has many meanings depending on the situation and community. Beyond the most obvious definition of open-source software and hardware, openness can also refer to inclusion of different groups of people as well as the openness of economic structures and spaces of entrepreneurship. As the maker movement, when understood as a global network of makers and different spaces for making, innovation and tinkering, is very diverse, it also comes with its tensions. These include tensions that arise from different imaginaries and scenarios as well as tensions that derive from balancing between individual and collective aims and needs (Saari et al. 2021).

The maker movement has been praised for its democratization potential, of the production process as well as of skills acquisition. Making empowers people to be creative and autonomous in solving any relevant local problem themselves, using machinery and materials at hand, adapting existing open designs, and sharing their innovations with a global community which does not discriminate between perceived experts and non-experts (Brady et al 2014; Bilandzic & Foth 2013, Keulartz & van den Belt 2016).

The democratizing power of makerspaces can also be seen in its results in making technology and its outcomes accessible for everyone. Makerspaces are supporting the creation of citizen science or social innovation projects, such as 3D-printed prosthetics, cheap sensor-based solutions for agriculture, and making technological solutions affordable for low-income people. There are a lot of makerspaces that create communities for their members, contribute to the improvement of the lives of people, or help them understand that technology does not need to be an inaccessible black box. At the same time, we also see modes of social critique in hacker- and makerspaces. Media art, fine art and other interactive artists have e.g. adopted maker practices and technologies to highlight critical stances within their work, using making as a mode of revealing a critical approach to embedded technological systems (Stoyanova 2017).

Narratives celebrating the maker movement even speak about a new industrial revolution (Anderson 2012), and the democratization of innovation and technology design by empowering the consumer (Tanenbaum et al. 2013) to make their own products through prosumerism (Paltrinieri and Esposti 2013). Maker communities have been celebrated for their potential for far-reaching social (Unterfrauner et al. 2019; Bosse et al. 2019), political (Maxigas 2012), and environmental (Lange 2017; Kohtala 2016) impacts. Makerspaces don't necessarily self-identify as spaces of social innovation, but some specialize in solving societal issues by engaging in certain activities.

At the same time, with the increasing popularity of the maker movement, criticisms have surfaced. Expectations have been high, but even with tens of thousands of workshops around the world, making remains a fringe phenomenon and the above mentioned new industrial revolution (Anderson 2012) has been difficult to prove (Troxler and Maxigas 2014). Similarly, concerns about unquestioned technosolutionism, namely the belief that technology can unilaterally solve all of society's problems have surfaced (Lindtner et al. 2016).

The social impact of makers in Western countries may be limited by the mainstream rhetoric of the entrepreneur maker and the standard engineering practices of their educational backgrounds. Thus, we need to ask: if innovating for society is a main goal of maker communities, who does it and how do practitioners innovate and engage in multidisciplinary processes that include critical thinking, reflexivity, and co-creation with others? One potential answer we see is *critical making*, a practice that was developed to unite critical thinking and the material practice of making (Ratto and Hockema 2009).

2.2 Critical Making

The Critical Making project¹³ emerged from the gap that research on the potential democratization power of the maker movement has still been scarce until recently. Thus, a transdisciplinary team of researchers and makers jointly launched a participatory research agenda at the start of 2021 to study grassroots innovation processes encountered in the maker community.

The project was inspired by the concept of *critical making*. Albeit still a niche approach, it has had a major impact on the design of the project. As briefly highlighted above, the term *critical making* was coined to describe an innovative approach to scholarship (Ratto and Hockema 2009) combining critical thinking and making to help engineering students understand so-called wicked problems. This idea was based on critical technical practice, aiming to bridge disciplinary mindsets as a precondition to hybrid multidisciplinary practices in technology development (Agre 1997). Later, it was extended towards grassroots

¹³ <https://criticalmaking.eu/>

approaches and critical citizenship, which have been described through the terms “maktivism” and “DIY citizenship” (Ratto and Boler 2014). Subsequently, the term was adapted to look beyond the idealized picture of the maker and to “reintroduce a sense of criticality back into post-2010 maker culture to un-sanitize, un-smooth and re-politicize it” (Hertz 2015). Hertz encouraged a type of making different from mainstream making, which dares to express political critique through art, activism, and social innovation. Ratto extended critical making as a practice “from academic critique to situated intervention” (Ratto 2016), working with a non-profit social enterprise, developing personalized 3D-printed prosthetics for people in Uganda and Cambodia. Finally, the term was co-creatively explored to understand whether it resonated with makers working outside of Western makerspaces (Sipos and Wenzelmann 2021). Thus, in terms of maker activities outside of academia, the term has been developing towards a better understanding of citizen’s practices and situated intervention outside of academia, as well as an encouragement of makers to express more critique through their material practice.

3 Towards a Critical Making Responsibility Framework

In the Critical Making project, the “critical” in “critical making” refers to the exploration of makers’ approaches to critical thinking and reflexivity about responsibility. The Critical Making Responsibility Framework, which is work in progress, draws from the analytical framework proposed to research grassroots innovation movements (GIM, Smith et al. 2016) to understand the social embeddedness of maker movement and puts that into dialogue with concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) capabilities developed within the European-centric research policy debates on responsibility of innovations (e.g. Stilgoe, Owen, and Macnaghten 2013). Combining these two conceptual/analytical approaches into the Critical Making Responsibility Framework aims to help researchers in participatory action research projects to better understand the criticality, reflexivity, and responsible practices of innovation within grassroots, involving the points of view of grassroots practitioners. At the same time, the consortium aims to provide a practical version of the framework as a critical reflection tool to makers and maker communities.

3.1 RRI capacities in grassroots innovations

RRI is a concept originally developed for the specific context of EU research and innovation funding (e.g. Gianni et al. 2019). The need for a new framework arose from the critical notions within science and technology studies claiming that research and innovation activities are not always well-aligned with the needs and realities of citizens and researchers should consider them more (e.g. Irwin 1995). It has been claimed that a closer connection between society and science is needed (Gibbons 1999), as the results of research are often ambiguous: they bring about better standards of life, but as by-products they also produce some considerable societal risks. The RRI framework therefore highlights the importance of engaging the public into scientific and innovation processes (e.g. Stilgoe et al. 2014) and the need for building capacities for successful encounters between science and society (e.g. Selin et al. 2017; Tassone et al. 2018).

The RRI approach has been organized around six policy keys, namely gender, governance, ethics, stakeholder and public engagement, and science education. These six keys come with their own sets of indicators that can be used in evaluation of science and innovation activities.¹⁴ The RRI framework also has the aspect of building capacities for a more reflexive, inclusive, anticipatory, and responsive future. These capabilities form the RRI capacity framework (see Figure 1; Tassone et al. 2018). We use the RRI capabilities framework to create a new understanding of the responsibility questions important in grassroots innovation communities.

¹⁴ See for example <https://rri-tools.eu/> and <https://wbc-rri.net/tag/rri-keys/>

So far, RRI tools and indicators have been mostly built for institutionalized settings of research and innovation. The viewpoints of grass-roots communities and small-scale innovation have not been considered in depth (Mamidipudi and Frahm 2020). The RRI framework has also been criticized for being Euro-centric (Bhaduri and Talat 2020), as it fails to recognize concepts such as grassroots and frugal innovation, which are especially prominent in the Global South (Mamidipudi and Frahm 2020). Currently available RRI tools and indicators are thus difficult to apply in the context of the global maker movement. However, we deem the RRI framework to be tailorable for diverse contexts. As we combine the four RRI capacities with the framework of Grassroots Innovation Movements, we believe the RRI frame will offer fruitful perspectives and new insights. Grass-roots innovations are more closely tied to the contexts of innovation compared to traditional, institutionalized research and innovation activities, and thus a fresh perspective has to be deployed.

Figure 1: RRI Competences (Source: Tassone et al. 2018)

3.2 Grassroots innovation movements analytical framework

Grassroots innovation, as opposed to mainstream innovation, is a phenomenon that has gained ample research interest in the past decades (e.g. Hess 2009 or Smith 2005). The term refers to innovation activities outside of formal institutions, often done by and for citizens to answer direct, immediate, contextual needs and problems. Grassroots innovation movements as a concept has been used to describe different makerspaces, hackerspaces, and other spaces of small-scale, grassroots innovation communities around the world. Central values widely shared by such spaces are open sharing of designs and cooperative nature of working, where innovative solutions are developed as a community effort. The strength of these communities is their adaptive and responsive nature, as they are generally able to change and adapt faster than institutionalized, large innovation units.

To better understand the grassroots innovation movements, Smith et al. (2016) developed the Grassroots Innovation Movements framework (GIM). The framework includes four distinct yet interrelated aspects, namely pathways, spaces and strategies, context and framings. Each of these dimensions acts as a lens through which different aspects affecting the development of grassroots innovation movements can be analysed. The aim of this framework is to provide researchers with a set of aspects that can help better understand the developments of such movements over time, often retrospectively. Smith et al. (2017) applied it to show the diverse landscape of making in Western countries, while Arancio (2021) applied GIM to analyse the Global Open Science Hardware (GOSH) movement.

Figure 2: The GIM framework in relation to RRI & Social Responsibility. The Consortium's illustration.

We use the GIM framework in combination with the RRI capacities framework to make it more concretely usable for steering the grass-roots movements into desirable futures. However, it is not our aim to use the tool as researchers from outside these movements, but to build it to be an useful and empowering tool for the grassroots movements themselves. For this purpose, combining the specific developmental dimensions of the GIM framework with the forward-looking capabilities of RRI is regarded as a fruitful approach.

3.3 The Critical Making Responsibility Framework

Based on these two approaches of RRI and GIM the Critical Making consortium came forward with a matrix combining GIM dimensions and RRI competences. This matrix includes short descriptions of each created intersection, picturing what the combination of different aspects could mean in practice (see Table 1). Overall, the matrix consists of 14 fields instead of 16, as the combination of RRI and GIM was deemed not applicable in two cases¹⁵ (Sipos et al. 2022b).

Combining all aspects clearly resulted in a lengthy, onerous, cognitively demanding exercise and a complex matrix, which does not lend itself easily for practical purposes. Thus, we build on a transdisciplinary co-creation process to further develop the matrix into a useful tool for makers, as outlined in the next sections.

¹⁵ See the published toolkit which is available under <https://zenodo.org/record/5948298#.YysuWC222i4>. The relevant part can be found under Chapter 5: Critical Making Responsibility Framework.

	Anticipation	Reflexivity	Inclusiveness	Responsiveness
Context	Ability to understand and act upon the ongoing changes in social, historical, political, economic, cultural, religious contexts (trends & weak signals) and other circumstances and what kind of opportunities, restrictions and requirements they may provide in the future.	To become aware of how social, historical, political, economic, cultural and religious context have affected on ones activities (innovations, projects etc.) and what kinds of contexts their reactions & innovations might create, (eg. vicious circles or hope, and for whom?)	To become aware of exclusive, contextual patterns - to understand that you don't by accident exclude others (like women, elderly, etc) - understanding how exclusion works and supporting people based on the contextual patterns of exclusion	To understand the particular societal needs arising from the context and to respond to them through making & innovations and in addition knowing "how to react and whom to contact to influence the societal rules of the game.
Framings	not applicable	To become aware of how used language and terminology shapes the actions taken and what kinds of values and interests are mobilized, maintained or challenged with the language used. Shared framings can help and hinder dialogues and once that is recognized, something new can be learned.	To reflect upon and become aware of the wordings that are used, or the setup of the space, and whether they create inclusion or exclusion? Does the shared umbrella of interpretation lead to missing any perspectives?	not applicable
Spaces/ Strategies	To become aware of one's own strategies to act, to learn to deliberately build strategies towards desired futures and to be able to anticipate what kinds of futures (and future spaces of action) the applied strategies create.	To become aware of how chosen strategies influence other people or environment - what are the risks and rewards for the surrounding community and environment of the chosen strategies	To become aware of the norms and conventions that "made the space" of making & innovations: if excludes someone, become aware of these norms and conventions, physical structures and language.	To explore how available resources will influence what you do (skills in the team; tools available) and how to act to expand them.
Pathways	To become more aware of what sort of pathways are supported: what future pathways are made while doing concrete projects, and reflect upon the potential plurality of it, to anticipate the impact of the ethical pathways. To recognize the path dependencies, become aware of what one can change with the created pathway and what not.	To become aware of one's own role and the situatedness of the activities carried out: how those impact/influence the environment. By recognizing the various pathways (anticipation), the potential social and ecological impacts can be reflected upon.	To reflect upon whether the developed or imagined pathways maintain existing exclusive structures, do they create new exclusions, new divisions between people? How can they be made more inclusive?	To investigate what kind of support the desired pathways would need in the broader social context (knowledge, funding, policy changes etc.) and/ or whether they may face resistance and to consider how this support can be gained and resistance addressed.

Table 1: GIM x RRI Matrix (Sipos et al. 2022b)

4 Reflective participatory co-creation process

In the Critical Making project, we follow a participatory approach that is strongly engaging representatives from the maker communities in all phases of the project. To build the Critical Making knowledge-base and advance it with original evidence, we apply a mixed method approach, based on participation, and inspired by participatory action research. This enables us as a consortium to collect data, analyse it, actively improve practices, and develop theories and synthesize findings with representatives from both, grassroots innovators from global maker communities and social innovation academics.

The theoretical framework presented above was inspired by existing maker practices aimed at supporting self-reflection, such as the set of "Sustainable Making Principles" (Nuesse and Wanalo 2019). Based on these principles and an initial workshop with global makers where different facets of critical making practices were reflected, the critical making consortium came forward with a working definition for responsibility in making and grassroots innovations. This initial definition refers to the following: Responsible innovation and making in grassroots practices means that those who tinker with existing technologies and develop new solutions do this critically. This criticality reflects on their responsibility to ensure that the solutions are:

- locally situated and community-based
- responsible, ethically correct and addressing societal needs
- based on critical thoughts and reflections about power structures
- aim to have positive impact and change structures
- and the practice itself is joyful and meaningful to the makers (Sipos et al. 2022a)

Adding the working definition with the state-of-the-art analysis on critical making practices and adding the theoretical constructs of RRI and GIM lead to the first GIM x RRI matrix or Critical Making Framework. The aim of the original matrix was to explore how the forward looking and reflexive RRI principles and retrospective GIM framework enrich each other. We have particularly wanted to understand and explore which dimensions align with each other and which might not. In total, eight multidisciplinary researchers with backgrounds in social sciences and STS, experience with maker communities, GIM and/or RRI, as well as disciplinary foci on gender, education and specializations in open source technology and development shared their experiences during this step of the process. They explored the feasibility and opportunities of developing the matrix and engaged in discussions on its usefulness and practicalities of implementation.

As a next step this theoretical construct, which was already an outcome of a collaborative effort, was put to test by filling it with examples and exemplary triggering questions in a reflexive exchange with makers. This was seen as a first attempt to support the understanding and the thought process of the future users of the framework. The initial examples and questions were mostly generated by practitioners engaged in Critical Making project activities. As some of those engaged in the global case actions work in complicated political contexts the cases are anonymized to protect the identities of those who could be negatively affected by having their names or projects revealed.

As the first framework ended in a large set of highly complex and partly overlapping questions, a next reflection round with a selected group of makers was initiated. It led to a critical revision of the matrix approach and the generation of applicable scenarios for the future use of the framework and the leading reflective questions.

Overall, this co-creation approach of the framework and the reflective questions involved more than 50 individuals from global maker communities and related practices. Due to the pandemic, interactions were mostly done in online sessions, such as the initial co-creation workshop in April 2021 or a dedicated workshop to discuss in detail about examples and reflective questions in September 2022. In addition to the online encounters, informal feedback was also collected during various face-to-face encounters, such as consortium meetings or the re:publica 2022 event in Berlin, where a panel and multiple workshops related to the work done in the Critical Making project were held.

The co-creation of the Critical Making Responsibility Framework is a reflective circular process (Fig. 3) with various loops and the findings so far will feed into further reflections and enhancements. In the next section we will present the critical outcomes so far and the final section will discuss some very initial ideas on how the framework may develop further and become a useful tool for critical making practices in the future.

Figure 3: Cyclic process towards an actionable Critical Making Responsibility Framework.

5 Experiences from Co-creating a Critical Making Responsibility Framework

While the interactions and co-design process of the Critical Making Responsibility Framework has spanned over many months and includes various iterations and mostly unstructured reflective cycles, as described above, in this section we focus on the insights gained during a dedicated online workshop held in September 2022. This workshop was organized specifically to collect examples from experienced global makers (joining us online from Brazil, Germany, Namibia, and Singapore), to discuss leading questions for self-reflection, and to reflect on the potential usefulness and application scenarios of the framework in maker practices. To facilitate the discussion and make the process easier, questions were pre-selected by the authors of this paper. The interaction was facilitated using a collaborative white board online (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Online white Board supporting co-creation in the Critical Making Responsibility Framework workshop with makers.

After a general presentation of the framework workshop participants were asked to give examples for each of the four RRI competences (reflexivity, anticipation, inclusiveness, responsiveness) focusing on the four concepts of grassroots innovation movements (broader contexts, framings, spaces and strategies and pathways) one after the other. As a next step the pre-selected triggering questions were discussed to see whether they fit for self-reflection on the aspects or not (see Table 2).

GIM/RRI	Reflexivity	Anticipation	Inclusiveness	Responsiveness
Context	<i>What societal changes do you promote with your making practices?</i>	<i>What kinds of trends or development pathways enable or hamper your maker practices in the future?</i>	<i>Are there any cultural, economic or other contextual factors that exclude some groups (eg. women, people with disabilities etc.) from making? Can you do anything about that?</i>	<i>How do you answer the specific needs of your community?</i>
Framings	<i>How does the way you speak about your making affect the decisions you make?</i> <i>Do all parties understand the terminology you use similarly, or are there different understandings?</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>	<i>Is the language you use inclusive of different groups and people?</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>
Spaces & Strategies	<i>Have you considered social and ecological sustainability when planning your actions?</i>	<i>What is your strategy for sustaining your activities in the long run?</i>	<i>What might be particular barriers (also physical ones) for any societal groups to participate? How could these be overcome?</i>	<i>How can you (as a team) work to overcome material scarcities and/or lack of skills?</i>
Pathways	<i>How can you create a culture around making that encourages critical thinking and sustainability values while also being fun?</i>	<i>Are your actions creating a pathway towards the kind of future that you want to see (even if in a small way)?</i>	<i>Are you building towards a more inclusive future? For whom?</i>	<i>From which societal actors would you need support to realize the future you hope to see?</i>

Table 2: Initial reflexive questions that were discussed in the co-working workshop.

During the discussion, we paid particular attention to which proposed questions seemed to engage the minds of the makers, e.g. by triggering ideas, or the number of examples they were able to share from their own experiences. Some questions were easy for them to re-formulate, others were still somewhat detached from their everyday practice or existing reflections, hence, we saw a lot less engagement with those questions. Moreover, towards the end of the 3-hour workshop, the participants were getting tired, and we received less input than at the beginning. We can derive two hypotheses from this: first, that the questions proposed in the last round were potentially less well formulated or engaging than the first three rounds, or that the topic of “pathways” is not one people are either familiar with or can reflect upon in relation to spaces that are only a few years old - pathways is one of those topics in GIM that are easier to address in retrospect. The second hypothesis is that a 3-hour long reflexive workshop might be too demanding for people. We, the researchers, also encountered this problem as we developed the matrix and will be proposing solutions below.

Overall, the feedback received from the experienced makers on the framework itself and on the leading questions was very positive. All participating makers easily contributed to the matrix with examples from their own practices, making the applicability of the combined terms clearly visible. However, it was not always clear which RRI competence the example would mostly respond to (e.g. reflexivity and responsiveness was thought of as overlapping concepts), indicating that clearer definitions might be needed to distinguish them, which is an interesting finding to explore in the future.

Based on some *context*-related examples a discussion emerged around the aspects of *reflexivity*, which defines the competence of becoming aware of how your actions reflect the surrounding world and influence it, and *responsiveness*, defined as the capability to act to make a change when needed, and

different interpretations of the term. The “Computers against COVID” initiative of Salvage Garden in Singapore¹⁶ can be understood as an example of both competences. The local maker community collected donations of old, unused laptops and electronic devices and refurbished them. Not only did the initiative show a fast response to an unforeseen crisis by providing laptops to low income families, but it also showed the gaps of the digital readiness policies and promoted rapid action from the Ministry of Education. In addition, electronic waste material that was left over from the refurbishing process was collected and turned into useful devices again, such as speakers. So, the idea of repurposing of the spare parts and refurbishing bluetooth speakers was born from the reflection on the potential negative impact of creating e-waste.

When discussing the RRI competences with regards to their possible *framings* we realized that there was a discrepancy between the provided examples and the guiding questions. While the examples also included aspects of underlying assumptions and narratives the questions were mostly focusing on the responsible way of how to use language and how to communicate with others. A good example that was brought up in the context of framing and inclusiveness was to think not only of who is participating in certain activities and workshops, but also who is running those activities: a maker posed the self-reflexive question “how could someone think of whom they are excluding if they are not excluding them consciously?” With this question, the legitimacy of the framework as a prompt to start those discussions was reassured.

An important discussion also emerged around the aspect of *spaces & strategies*. While most of the initial pre-selected questions were formulated having individual makers or maker communities in mind, we realized that especially this point should include some questions that are targeting teams running makerspaces. Discussions took place around what constitutes a “community”, which, to some, means an established group of people. Here one might think about the “membership” of a makerspace instead if the human connection that forges a community has not been established yet. Previously, similar concerns about “citizens” were expressed, as e.g. in the case of a project working with refugees, they might not be citizens of the place where the project is located. Moreover, recommendations were shared to address a town or city instead, where the makerspace is located. For example, if they grow a community around a certain project or local space, it is important to consider who they take money from to sustain the activities (in this case, e.g. the municipality of the town), as funding often comes with expectations from the funder’s side.

The most difficult aspect for the makers to come up with examples and reflect on their practice, was the future looking dimension of *pathways*. This is completely reasonable, as in GIM, pathways are most easy to utilize retrospectively. Difficulties might arise especially if the framework should be applied as a planning tool it is difficult to distinguish between pathways, which refers to alternative actions for possible futures, and strategies, which would be the concrete and deliberate ways one would plan to take in order to achieve a certain objective. A guiding question that came out of the discussion to support critical thinking in terms of pathways has been formulated as follows: “*How do you create alternatives to the prominent way of doing things?*”.

After going through the whole matrix by adding examples and reflecting on the questions, a refined set of questions had emerged (see Table 3). Most of the initial questions were changed in the process, although a few were accepted by the makers in the original form. The set of questions we have after the workshop is more understandable for makers and better reflects the complex intersections of different GIM and RRI dimensions, likely generating even richer reflections on different themes.

¹⁶ <https://salvage.garden/>

GIM/RRI	Reflexivity	Anticipation	Inclusiveness	Responsiveness
Context	What societal changes do you promote with your making practices?	<i>How do you future proof your practice?</i>	<i>Who is giving workshops or teaching in your space? Is it managed so that everyone can feel comfortable in the space?</i>	<i>What actions/steps can you take to better understand societal needs? How does this shape the actions you intend to take?</i>
Framings	<i>How does the way you speak about your making practice affect the decisions you make?</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>	<i>When presenting your space, are you choosing narratives/stories that are inclusive?</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>
Spaces & Strategies	Have you considered social and ecological sustainability when planning your actions?	<i>Who do you take money and/or resources from and how does that affect your making practices?</i>	What might be particular barriers (also physical ones) for any societal groups to participate? How could these be overcome?	<i>How can you work to overcome material scarcities and/or lack of skills in your project?</i>
Pathways	<i>How can you create and support alternatives to prominent ways of doing things?</i>	<i>Are your actions contributing to the kind of future that you want to see (even if in a small way)?</i>	Are you building towards a more inclusive future? For whom?	From which public or private societal actors (e.g. companies, politicians, schools) would you need support to realize the future you hope to see?

Table 3: Elaborated reflexive questions after the workshop.

In a final round of brainstorming and reflection, the overall usefulness of the framework for makers and how it could be made appealing to them was discussed. These preliminary ideas makers shared with us of how the framework could become useful and remain a fun activity to engage with will be explained in the next section.

6 Towards a Maker-Friendly Tool

The creation of the initially theory-driven Critical Making Responsibility Framework and the attempts to turn it into a reflexive tool to support makers' sustainability has included many rounds of co-design and co-creation, as we have deemed it important to engage makers in the process. When producing a tool to be used by practitioners, it is crucial to engage them in the process to ensure that what we produce is meaningful, understandable, and attractive for them. To fit the tool for different contexts globally, we also tried to engage a diverse group of co-researchers, makers and makerspace leaders from different contexts and places. The work of elaborating the GIM-RRI matrix and related set of reflection questions into a tool usable in maker contexts is continuing, and more interaction with makers is still needed in the future to ensure the relevancy of our work.

As explained in this article, we departed from the scientific RRI and GIM frameworks that we believed could bring useful insights if brought together. The challenge has been the academic nature of both frameworks: they use academic language, difficult terminology and include complex concepts. Bringing them together and building an easy-to-use practical tool for non-academics who have different socioeconomic backgrounds and speak different languages is a challenge. That is also why we have made a considerable effort to explain the terminology, simplify the language and challenge our own thinking by engaging with makers. Engaging makers who work on diverse cultural settings and with diverse groups of people to provide input for us and ultimately to co-design a new set of reflection questions has been an invaluable help in bringing the tool closer to actual contexts of use.

To make the Critical Making Responsibility Framework useful for makers is not only dependent on the formulation of questions. In the next step, we also need to develop a concept of how the framework is

used by makers, how the reflexive process is implemented in practice and what could motivate makers to engage in responsibility (self-)evaluation. Here, we face the fundamental dilemma of implementing critical thinking in making without taking the fun out of maker practices. As researchers, we have a significantly different view on responsibility compared to makers, whose main interest is often to build things. To successfully translate the academic concepts into a tool for practitioners, we need to be aware of these differences in thinking.

So far, the feedback we have gotten from makers has been encouraging. The makers we have engaged with have expressed interest in using the reflexive questions to develop their working styles and to generate new discussions around the themes. In the workshop, the participating makers also found the reflexive questions to be fruitful in the sense that they triggered new thoughts and opened new viewpoints to responsibility. We have already gained interest towards our reflection tool from very different contexts, as makers from e.g. Singapore, Germany and Finland have explicitly said they would be interested in using the tool in the future, if an easy-to-use version were to be distributed.

However, to make this happen we still need to figure out how to make a version of the tool that would be motivating and even fun to use. Some initial ideas, which have to be further explored, prototyped and tested are for example to turn the questions into an online test, to gamify the approach and have it e.g. as physical playing cards in maker spaces and to translate the framework and questions into other languages and cultural contexts. Another question was raised around the possible usefulness of Critical Making badges to be obtained by going through the guiding questions. Maybe such a badge could add additional credibility for obtaining funding for future projects. However, we still see the tool mostly for self-reflection and by no means does the Critical Making consortium see itself as an authority who would decide on what is critical making and what is not. The final form of the reflexive tool will be defined later, as our work inside the consortium and together with makers continues.

It was also stressed in the workshop that to find the reflexive questions meaningful and inspiring, makers should have internal motivation to become more responsible in the first place. The makers we have engaged with so far have been diverse in many aspects, but they cannot be interpreted as a representative sample of makers' attitudes towards responsibility, critical thinking, or reflexive tools like the one we intend to develop. Therefore, it is central that we find the right channels to reach the makers who would want to get help in becoming more critical and responsible.

As we continue our work, we will test and define a format to present the questions that will be easy enough to use, inspiring and meaningful for makers looking for support in enhancing their practice. As we test preliminary versions of a tool based on this framework, we will also refine the questions as needed, based on the feedback we gather. We will also pay attention to testing the questions with a diverse group of makers to ensure it resonates to different practitioners. The tool will also be translated to different languages to test its usability in different languages, such as German and Finnish. Different maker communities will still be engaged in different phases and feedback will be gathered. Our aim is to co-create a tool with makers for makers to enhance their critical thinking and ultimately their sustainability practices.

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References

- Agre, P. E. 1997. "Toward a Critical Technical Practice: Lessons Learned in Trying to Reform AI." In *Social Science, Technical Systems and Cooperative Work: Beyond the Great Divide*, edited by Geoffrey C. Bowker, Les Gasser, Susan Leigh Star, and William Turner, 131–57. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Anderson, C.: Makers. The New Industrial Revolution. Crown Publishing Group, New York, 2012.

Regina Sipos, Maria Åkerman, Hanna Saari, Barbara Kieslinger: Critical Making Responsibility Framework. Extending an Academic Proposal to Support Reflexivity in Maker Communities

- Arancio, Julieta Cecilia. 2021. "Opening Up the Tools for Doing Science: The Case of the Global Open Science Hardware Movement." *International Journal of Engineering, Social Justice and Peace* 8(2): 1–27.
- Benchoff, B. (2016). The MakerBot Obituary. <https://hackaday.com/2016/04/28/the-makerbot-obituary>
- Bilandzic, M. & Foth, M.: Libraries as co-working spaces: understanding user motivations and perceived barriers to social learning. *Library Hi Tech*, 31 (2), 2013.
- Bosse, I, D Krüger, H Linke, and B Pelka. 2019. "The Maker Movement's Potential for an Inclusive Society.," *Atlas of social innovation. A world of new practices*, no. 2nd Volume: 201–6.
- Brady, T., Salas, C., Nuriddin, A., Rodgers, W., & Subramaniam, M.: *MakeAbility: Creating accessible makerspace events in a public library*. *Public Library Quarterly*, 33(4), 2014.
- Dreessen, K., Schepers, S., & Leen, D. 2016. From Hacking Things to Making Things. *Rethinking making by supporting non-expert users in a FabLab*. *IxD&A*, 30(2016), 47-64.
- Fasoli, A.; Tassinari, S. Engaged by design: the role of emerging collaborative infrastructures for social development. Roma makers as a case study. *The Design Journal* 2017 sup1, S3121–S3133.
- Gianni, R., Pearson, J., & Reber, B. 2019. *Responsible Research and Innovation*. Routledge, Abingdon-on-Thames.
- Gibbons, M. 1999. Science's new social contract with society. *Nature*, 402(6761), C81-C84.
- Haldrup, M., Hoby, M., & Padfield, N. 2018. The bizarre bazaar: FabLabs as hybrid hubs. *CoDesign*, 14(4), 329-344.
- Halverson, E.R. & Sheridan, K.: *The Maker Movement in Education*. *Harvard Educational Review: December 2014*, Vol. 84, No. 4, pp. 495-504., 2014
- Hertz, G., ed 2015: *Conversations in Critical Making*. *Blueshift Series*, CTheory Books.
- Hess, David J. 2009a. "David J . Hess: Alternative Pathways in Science and Industry: Activism, Innovation and the Environment in an Era of Globalization *The MIT Press : Cambridge , Massachusetts 2007 . 334 Pages*" 22 (1): 64–66.
- Irwin, A.: *Citizen Science. A Study of People, Expertise and Sustainable Development*. Routledge, London. 1995.
- Johns, J., & Hall, S. M. 2020. 'I have so little time [...] I got shit I need to do': Critical perspectives on making and sharing in Manchester's FabLab. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 52(7), 1292-1312.
- Keulartz J, & van den Belt, H.: *DIY-Bio-economic, epistemological and ethical implications and ambivalences*. *Life Sciences, Society and Policy*. 2016 Dec;12(1):7. doi: 10.1186/s40504-016-0039-1
- Kieslinger B, Schaefer T, Fabian CM, Biasin E, Bassi E, Freire RR, Mowoh N, Arif N and Melis P (2021) Covid-19 Response From Global Makers: The Careables Cases of Global Design and Local Production. *Front. Sociol.* 6:629587. doi: 10.3389/fsoc.2021.629587
- Kohtala, C. 2016. "Making Sustainability: How Fablabs Address Environmental Issues (Doctoral D)." Helsinki: Aalto University Publication.
- Lange, B. 2017. "Offene Werkstätten Und Postwachstumsökonomien: Kollaborative Orte Als Wegbereiter Transformativer Wirtschaftsentwicklungen?" *Zeitschrift Für Wirtschaftsgeographie*, no. 61(1): 38–55.
- Langley, D.J.; Zirngiebl, M.; Sbeih, J.; Devoldere, B. Trajectories to reconcile sharing and commercialization in the maker movement. *Business Horizons* 2017 60(6), 783–794
- Lindtner, S., Bardzell, S. and Bardzell, J. 2016. "Reconstituting the Utopian Vision of Making: HCI after Technosolutionism." In *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems—Proceedings*, 1390–1402. Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2858036.2858506>
- Mamidipudi, A., & Frahm, N. 2020. Turning straw to gold: mobilising symmetry in responsible research and innovation. *Science, Technology and Society*, 25(2), 223-239.
- Maxigas, Peter. 2012. "Hacklabs and Hackerspaces: Tracing Two Genealogies." *Journal of Peer Production* No. 2 (July). <http://peerproduction.net/issues/issue-2/peer-reviewed-papers/hacklabs-and-hackerspaces>
- Millard, J.; Sorivelle, M.N.; Deljanin, S.; Unterfrauner, E.; Voigt, C. Is the Maker Movement Contributing to Sustainability? *Sustainability* 2018, 10, 2212
- Menichinelli, M., Schmidt, A.G.S.(2019). *Measuring the Social Impact of Maker Initiatives. Frameworks and Guidelines for Scaling the Assessment on Digital Platforms*. Conference: International Conference Sharing Society, May 2019.

Regina Sipos, Maria Åkerman, Hanna Saari, Barbara Kieslinger: Critical Making Responsibility Framework. Extending an Academic Proposal to Support Reflexivity in Maker Communities

- Nuesse, I., and Wanalo, R. 2019. "How Can Makerspaces Help Build Climate Change Resilience?" <https://wellbeingeconomy.org/how-can-makerspaces-help-build-climate-change-resilience>
- Paltrinieri, R. and Esposti, P.D. 2013. "Processes of Inclusion and Exclusion in the Sphere of Prosumerism," *Future Internet*, MDPI, vol. 5(1), pages 1-13, January.
- Ratto, M. 2016. "Making at the End of Nature". In *Interactions: Vol. 23. (5): 26-35*. DOI: 10.1145/2985851
- Ratto, M., and Boler, M. (eds). 2014. *DIY Citizenship. Critical Making and Social Media*. The MIT Press.
- Ratto, M., and Hockema, S., 2009. "FLWR PWR—Tending the Walled Garden." Edited by A Dekker and A Saari, H.; Åkerman, M.; Kieslinger, B.; Myllyoja, J.; Sipos, R. (2021). How Open Is the Maker Movement? Integrative Literature Review of the Openness Practices in the Global Maker Movement. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 13559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132413559>
- Selin, C., Rawlings, K. C., de Ridder-Vignone, K., Sadowski, J., Altamirano Allende, C., Gano, G., ... & Guston, D. H. 2017. Experiments in engagement: Designing public engagement with science and technology for capacity building. *Public Understanding of Science*, 26(6), 634-649.
- Sipos, R, Åkerman, M & Wenzelmann, V. (2022a). Critical Making Baseline. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6907490>
- Sipos, R., Kieslinger, B., Schaefer, T., Seebacher, L. M., Åkerman, M., & Mamitzsch, S. (2022b). Critical Making Case Actions and Methodologies: A Methodological Toolbox. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5948298>
- Sipos R. and Wenzelmann, V. 2021. "Critical Making With and For Communities: Community–Driven Critical Making Grounded in Practitioners' Perspectives on Definition and Praxis." In . Seattle, USA <https://doi.org/10.1145/3461564.3461572>.
- Smith, A. 2005. "The Alternative Technology Movement: An Analysis of Its Framing and Negotiation of Technology Development." *Human Ecology Review* 12 (2): 106–19.
- Smith, A., Fressoli, J.M., Abrol, D., Arond, E. and Ely, A. (2016). *Grassroots Innovation Movements*. Routledge, Earthscan.
- Stilgoe, J., Owen, R., & Macnaghten, P.: Developing a framework for responsible innovation. In: *Research Policy*, 42(9), 1568-1580. 2013.
- Stilz, M. (2021). Review of Measures to Integrate Young People into the Maker Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5535614>
- Stoyanova, Minka. 2017. "Reading Makers." *Digital Culture & Society* 3 (1). <https://doi.org/10.14361/dcs-2017-0105>.
- Tassone, V. C., O'Mahony, C., McKenna, E., Eppink, H. J., & Wals, A. E. 2018. (Re-) designing higher education curricula in times of systemic dysfunction: a responsible research and innovation perspective. *Higher Education*, 76(2), 337-352.
- Tanenbaum, T.J., Williams, A. M., Desjardins, A., & Tanenbaum, K. (2013, April). Democratizing technology: pleasure, utility and expressiveness in DIY and maker practice. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 2603-2612).
- Troxler, P. and Maxigas. 2014. "Editorial Note: We Now Have the Means of Production, but Where Is My Revolution?" *Journal of Peer Production*, no. 5: 11–13.
- Unterfrauner, E., Voigt, C. and Hofer, M. 2019. "Participative Evaluation with Children in Educational Maker Projects Experiences from a Pilot Action." *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 194–97. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3328320.3328372>.
- Vuorikari, R., Ferrari, A., & Punie, Y.: Makerspaces for Education and Training. Exploring future implications for Europe. Science for Policy report by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. 2019. https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC117481/makerspaces_2034_education.pdf
- Wolfsberger. *Walled Garden*, Virtueel Platform, The Netherlands, , 51–62.